

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc
hash://md5/3045b5e1daee01da6abfeba28c1d37dd

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc, has fingerprint hash://md5/3045b5e1daee01da6abfeba28c1d37dd, is 104MiB in size and contains 309,223 interactions with 4 unique types of associations (e.g., hasHost) between 11,328 primary taxa (e.g., SH1255416.10FU) and 351 associated taxa (e.g., Pinus sylvestris). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Cortinariarius barcoding database of Western Siberia and adjacent areas - Version 1.23 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=cortdb2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z> Ectoparasites of *Zootoca vivipara* (Lichtenstein, 1823) in Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug - Version 1.7 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=lizardmites2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z> eDNA-based occurrence dataset on fungi of fine woody debris studied in Northwestern Siberia - Version 1.3 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=mycopins2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z> eDNA-based occurrence dataset on peatland fungal communities studied by metabarcoding in Northwestern Siberia - Version 1.23 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=bogfunmeta2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z> Endoparasites of amphibians of the city of Surgut - Version 1.8 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=amphibiaparasites2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z> Fungal Culture Collection of Yugra State University - Version 1.13 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=ysuculturecollection2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z> Fungal literature records database of the Northern West Siberia (Russia) - Version 1.22 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=fredy>

2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z New Larix-associated Suillus species (Boletales, Agaricomycetes) from North Asia - Version 1.5 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=kovalenkoi> 2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z New species of macromycetes for regions of the Russian Far East - 2022 - Version 1.2 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=fareastfungi22> 2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z New species of macromycetes for regions of the Russian Far East - Version 1.2 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=fareastfungi> 2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z The Fungal Literature-based Occurrence Database for the Southern West Siberia (Russia) - Version 1.23 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=funsws> 2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z The Fungarium of Yugra State University - Version 1.258 <http://ipt.ugrasu.ru:8080/archive.do?r=fungariumysu> 2026-06-02T23:14:33.542Z hash://md5/3045b5e1daee01da6abfeba28c1d37dd

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 104MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc
```

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc`)

```

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv

```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in [Appendix A. Review Files](#).

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc`, has fingerprint hash://md5/3045b5e1daee01da6abfeba28c1d37dd, is 104MiB in size and contains 309,223 interactions with 4 unique types of associations (e.g., `hasHost`) between 11,328 primary taxa (e.g., `SH1255416.10FU`) and 351 associated taxa (e.g., `Pinus sylvestris`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
SH1233742.10FU	hasHost	Pinus sylvestris	Bog-fun-metabarcodes-000001
SH1239117.10FU	hasHost	Pinus sylvestris	Bog-fun-metabarcodes-000002
SH0214090.10FU	hasHost	Pinus sylvestris	Bog-fun-metabarcodes-000003

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
SH1843548.10FU	hasHost	Pinus sylvestris	Bog-fun- metabarcodes- 000004

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
hasHost	303255
parasiteOf	2856
adjacentTo	1810
interactsWith	1302

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
SH1255416.10FU	15847
SH0083069.10FU	6868
SH1315282.10FU	6132
Fungi	4573
SH1255022.10FU	4188
SH1255185.10FU	4024
SH1268841.10FU	3117
SH1255814.10FU	2935
SH0206607.10FU	2794
SH1290122.10FU	2701
SH1737283.10FU	2632
SH1255870.10FU	2627
SH1255230.10FU	2626
SH1367332.10FU	2344
SH1290110.10FU	2344
SH1255355.10FU	2201
SH1357235.10FU	2167
SH1314704.10FU	1996
SH1268845.10FU	1937

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Pinus sylvestris	38669
Ledum palustre	33823
Eriophorum vaginatum	33355
Sphagnum fuscum	20758
Chamaedaphne calyculata	19806
Scheuchzeria palustris	18671
Andromeda polifolia	18336
Betula	17766
Rubus chamaemorus	17489
Larix sibirica	17369
Sphagnum balticum	15728
Carex limosa	12605
Sphagnum jensenii	9624
Sphagnum angustifolium	7203
Pinus sibirica	6549
Sphagnum magellanicum	5889
Oxycoccus palustris	5597
Sphagnum papillosum	4334
Rana arvalis Nilsson	1371

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
SH1315282.10FU	hasHost	Pinus sylvestris	4806
SH1255416.10FU	hasHost	Pinus sylvestris	4110
SH0083069.10FU	hasHost	Scheuchzeria palustris	3798
SH1268841.10FU	hasHost	Ledum palustre	2425
SH1255416.10FU	hasHost	Betula	1943
SH1255814.10FU	hasHost	Eriophorum vaginatum	1893
SH0083069.10FU	hasHost	Eriophorum vaginatum	1822
SH1255416.10FU	hasHost	Larix sibirica	1757
SH1255022.10FU	hasHost	Carex limosa	1756
SH1290122.10FU	hasHost	Pinus sylvestris	1519
SH1255416.10FU	hasHost	Sphagnum fuscum	1479
SH1290110.10FU	hasHost	Rubus chamaemorus	1456
SH1255416.10FU	hasHost	Ledum palustre	1366
SH1268845.10FU	hasHost	Ledum palustre	1261
SH1255185.10FU	hasHost	Pinus sylvestris	1260

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
SH1315326.10FU	hasHost	Pinus sibirica	1220
SH1255416.10FU	hasHost	Chamaedaphne calyculata	1191
SH1255870.10FU	hasHost	Carex limosa	1018
SH1255355.10FU	hasHost	Sphagnum fuscum	1013

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

MAP

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

```

SIZE 1600 800
EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
END
LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
END
CLASS
    STYLE
        COLOR 232 232 232
        OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
END
LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
        STYLE
            COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
            DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 5.485732780437265
            RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
            OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
        END
    END
END
END
END

```

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Dolichosaccus rastellus	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Dolichosaccus rastellus
Dolichosaccus rastellus	SYNONYM_OF	col	Dolichosaccus rastellus
Haplometra cylindracea	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Haplometra cylindracea
Rhabdias bufonis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Rhabdias bufonis

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	10385
col	class	1
col	family	12
col	genus	97
col	kingdom	1
col	order	3
col	phylum	1
col	species	1010
col	subspecies	7
col	variety	2
discoverlife	NA	11515
gbif	NA	10374
gbif	class	1
gbif	family	12
gbif	form	5
gbif	genus	97
gbif	kingdom	1
gbif	order	3
gbif	phylum	1
gbif	species	1019
gbif	subspecies	16
gbif	variety	8
itis	NA	11345
itis	class	1
itis	division	1
itis	family	11
itis	genus	27
itis	kingdom	2
itis	order	3
itis	species	122
itis	subspecies	2
mdd	NA	11514
ncbi	NA	10527
ncbi	clade	1
ncbi	family	11
ncbi	genus	91
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	3
ncbi	phylum	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
ncki	species	878
ncki	subspecies	1
ncki	varietas	1
pbdb	NA	11484
pbdb	family	4
pbdb	genus	14
pbdb	kingdom	1
pbdb	order	1
pbdb	species	9
pbdb	unranked clade	1
tpt	NA	11509
tpt	species	5
wfo	NA	11432
wfo	family	1
wfo	genus	10
wfo	species	68
wfo	subspecies	2
wfo	variety	1
worms	NA	11366
worms	family	11
worms	genus	53
worms	kingdom	1
worms	order	3
worms	phylum (division)	1
worms	species	79

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1118
col	SYNONYM_OF	399
col	NONE	11611
discoverlife	NONE	12886
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	422
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1316
gbif	NONE	11602

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
itis	NONE	12675
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	191
itis	SYNONYM_OF	17
mdd	NONE	12882
ncbi	NONE	11762
ncbi	SAME_AS	1036
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	92
pbdb	NONE	12841
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	40
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	3
tpt	NONE	12877
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	2
wfo	NONE	12761
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	101
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	32
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	14
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	153
worms	NONE	12723
worms	SYNONYM_OF	13

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T04:36:09Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/ysu-bc/archive/7b54966d5aec35a2aba20679f3fbcba17e04226
2026-06-03T04:36:09Z	summary	309223 interaction(s)
2026-06-03T04:36:09Z	summary	0 note(s)
2026-06-03T04:36:09Z	summary	540 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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